

METHODS AND PERIOD OF MINTING COTTON

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ABSTRACT

Very famous scientists of our republic and cotton-growing countries of the world Bushuev M.M. (1913), Schroeder RR. (1913), Makarov A.F. (1930), Lysenko T.D. and others found that the importance of cleaning is high, it improves the quality of cotton and fiber. Academician Lysenko T.D. (1936) found that the growth and development of cotton improved as a result of culling, and shedding of combs and knots was reduced due to the redistribution of nutrients along the branches of the crop.

Keywords: research results, cotton ginning, agricultural technology, development, productivity.

On the basis of the results of a number of scientific studies conducted in Uzbekistan since 1939, on the basis of a special decision of the government of our Republic, ginning has been introduced as an important event that must be performed in the agrotechnics of cotton [1-3].

Along with all agrotechnical activities, timely and high-quality ginning of cotton ensures optimal growth and development of cotton, enhances the formation of crop elements and the appearance of bolls, bolls, flowers and shedding of nodes is reduced, the number and weight of bolls increase, early opening, high cotton yield, quality fiber and seed are produced [4,5].

The effect of cotton ginning periods on cotton yield. As a result of timely, correct and high-quality ginning, crop elements are less spilled, the growth and development of cotton is accelerated from 7-8 days to 10 days, productivity increases from 3-5 centners to 8 centners, cotton Fiber quality is 25. It improves by 30%, the weight of the seed increases, its moisture content increases by 1-2%, favorable conditions are created for planting autumn crops in optimal terms.

Hand spinning cotton. Cotton ginning is done manually in the fields by pinching three parts of the stem 1-1.5 cm. every worker who participates in manual pruning must wear an apron, and the tip of the pinched tuber must be taken out of the field and buried in the ground. In this way, the eggs of the bollworm at the end of the cotton are also taken out of the field. Hand-picking cotton in the first stage, the third part of the main stem is plucked, and in the second stage, after 7-8 days, short cottons and the tips of

the side branches are pinched. If the side branches are not pruned, they will grow and develop quickly and their rows will merge, they will shade, the pods in the lower layer will not mature, the pods will shrink, and some will rot [6,7].

For this reason, every farm manager and experts should educate the field workers before starting hand weeding and strengthen control during the weeding process.

Mechanically spinning the cotton relieves the hand cocktail. In this case, a special device hanging in front of the tractor cultivator is adjusted at a height of 80-100 cm, and during cultivation, the upper part of the cotton is cut with the help of special blades. In this method, it is necessary to re-prune both underdeveloped and side branches. Otherwise, the rows of cotton will quickly merge and the air exchange will deteriorate, which will have a negative effect on the pods in the lower layer. During threshing with the help of the mechanism, the ripe bolls, flowers and nodes of the cotton bushes with developed buds are cut by the blade, and the yield can be relatively reduced.

Chemical weeding of cotton is considered effective and convenient for cotton yield and optimal growth. The drugs recommended for chemical spraying are mixed with 250-300 liters of water per hectare in OVX and other spraying devices 5-7 days before or 5-7 days after irrigation. Chemical cleaning eliminates the heavy duty of manual cleaning. fuel consumption is saved 5-6 times compared to the engine.

In the regions of our republic, if Sojean, Entojean preparations are applied three times during the cotton vegetation period (heading, flowering, yielding) at the rate of 15+45+90 g/ha, or when 12-13 harvest branches are collected in cotton, 100- At the rate of 110 g/ha, Dalpix 1.0-1.5 league, Pix 1.5- At the rate of 2.0 l/ha, if it is sprinkled 5-7 days before or after watering the cotton, there is no need for manual weeding.

In Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions, the number of cotton varieties is 90-100 thousand plants per hectare in highly fertile soils, 13-14 per hectare, and 100 per hectare in moderately fertile soils. 12-13 per 110,000 bushes, 12-12 per hectare with 110-120,000 bushes per hectare, and 12-13 on well- maintained plots with 110-120,000 seedlings left on the ground with groundwater. it is chirping in the harvest branch. In these regions, if cotton is planted, it is necessary to carry out pruning when 10-11 harvest branches appear.

Advantages and Disadvantages of minting cotton:

as a result of timely, correct and high-quality weeding, crop elements are less spilled, the growth and development of cotton is accelerated by 7-8 days, the productivity is 5-8 s/ha and more. increases, cotton quality improves by 25-30%;

after pruning, all the necessary nutrients are directed to the fruit organs, not to the upper growth branches;

the number of bolls increases in the areas where chipping is carried out, the cotton opens early, and the weight of cotton in one boll increases;

cotton bollworm damage is reduced by 50-60%. When cotton is defoliated, the leaves shed well;

economic efficiency is achieved by selling a lot of cotton to high varieties.

Disadvantages:

if of minting cotton is not carried out, underground seepage water will flood cotton in nearby places, early if transferred, it will grow and branch;

in cotton, the bolls, flowers and buds (young bolls up to 10 days old) are shed and the yield is reduced to 20-30%;

the yield of cotton decreases by 15-20%, ripening is delayed by 7-10 days, the weight and size of bolls are reduced;

cotton is dense, delays boll opening, and attracts insects. increases, defoliation efficiency decreases.

In addition to the abundance of high-quality cotton in areas planted with Chilpish, it is possible to complete harvesting in a short period of time without delaying the rainy days, to sell the product to high varieties, to increase the economic efficiency, to harvest the autumn grain crops on time. planting is provided.

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